

Fig. S1 Landmark position of the tegminal samples of *Cycloscytina*. (a) right tegmen of STMN48-1827; (b) left tegmen of STMN48-1827; (c) right tegmen of STMN48-1830; (d) left tegmen of STMN48-1830; (e) right tegmen of NIGP05170; (f) left tegmen of NIGP05170; (g) NIGP05219 (holotype of *C. incompleta* sp. nov.); (h) holotype of *C. asiatica*, redrawn from Martynov (1937); (i) specimen of *C. delutinervis*, redrawn from Shcherbakov (1988a); (j) holotype of *C. extensa*, redrawn from Martynov (1937); (k) holotype of *C. gobiensis*, redrawn from Shcherbakov (1988b); (l) holotype of *C. korlaensis*, redrawn from Hong (1983).

References

Hong Y (1983) *Middle Jurassic fossil insects in north China*. Beijing: Geological Publishing House, 187 pp. (in Chinese)

Martynov AV (1937) Liassic insects from Shurab and Kisyl-Kiya, Part I, Various orders except Blattodea and Coleoptera. *Akademiya Nauk SSSR, Trudy Paleontologicheskogo Instituta* 7, 1–178.

Shcherbakov DE (1988a) New cicadas (Cicadina) from the Later Mesozoic of Transbaikalia. *Paleontological Journal* 22, 52–63.

Shcherbakov DE (1988b) New Mesozoic Homoptera In *New Species of Fossil Invertebrates of Mongolia* (ed. AY Rozanov). *Transactions of the Joint Soviet-Mongolian Paleontological Expedition* 33, 60–63. (in Russian)